

A multi-scale approach to snow cover observations and models (SnowCover)

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1. Highlights

- The description of the snow cover in the Arctic can be approached with different spatial and time scales. This large variability is not a weakness; rather, it represents a relevant opportunity to fill the multi-scale gap that affects snow cover monitoring.
- The availability of long time series is the key to observing long-term climate changes. A combination of different methodologies based on several data sources (terrestrial and satellite observations) is the most reliable solution.
- Terrestrial photography contributes by offering high-resolution and high temporally resolved ground truth for satellite imagery, but it is limited in terms of spatial extension. This approach is unaffected by cloud cover but requires a large number of observing sites distributed across the region.
- The long-term climate data record for the terrestrial snow cover in Svalbard with snow model output for snow water equivalent and in situ measurements of snow cover and snow-off dates are important for many scientific disciplines.
- Time series offer the opportunity to study the relationships between satellite observations and snow-related models.

2. Background

The snow cover can be studied by combining different data sources and integrating several data types. Snow cover data is relevant not only for the study of snow *per se*, but it is also used as input for different models (e.g. snow models) and to verify simulation output. Earth observation (EO) of snow involves the gathering of information on the physical properties of snow via remote sensing technologies as well as in situ measurements. Snow is characterised by many properties, including snow cover, snow depth, temperature, density, grain size, shape, etc. Different sensors have variable capabilities of measuring snow. In situ sensors or sensors close to the site measure the properties more efficiently, in terms of time resolution, than remote sensing at the cost of being only valid as a point measurement. Remote sensors cover a wider area but are usually less timely resolved. Spatial and temporal scales are the most critical features that must be taken into account in order to fill the existing gap between the different observation methods.

On the one hand, in situ point measurements can be extremely detailed over time but limited in terms

of spatial extension. On the other hand, satellite acquisitions can provide complete spatial coverage across Svalbard but have limitations associated with revisiting time and the cloud cover. In the past five years, since the deployment of the first Sentinel-2 platform, the gap between satellite and in situ observations has reduced thanks to technological improvements, with the availability of automated measurement stations on one side and, on the other, the introduction of new satellite platforms that are becoming more efficient in terms of numbers (constellations of platforms) and sensor capabilities. There have also been significant improvements in the range between satellite and in situ observations with the development of intermediate methodologies: airborne platforms, unmanned aerial vehicles, terrestrial photography, etc. All these approaches can contribute to the integration of new, recent and past observations.

This report includes three data summaries that contribute to this important task, focusing on integrating different data sources for the assessment of the state of the snow cover. The first (PASSES) provides a picture of terrestrial

photography applications focused on the snow cover with information about the facilities operated by different nationalities and the maturity level of datasets in terms of fractional snow cover retrieval. The second (SvalSCESIA) compares the existing satellite-based long-term climate data record for terrestrial snow cover in Svalbard with snow model output for snow water equivalent and in situ measurements of the snow cover and snow-off dates. Spatial and temporal trends are investigated and viewed in relation to trends in sea-ice area for the adjacent sea, derived from a long-term climate data record for sea-ice concentration. The third (SATMODSNOW) compares satellite observations

with outputs from hydrological snow models and quantifies the differences. All three present a full picture for every single approach and suggest the need for more efforts in the comparison between tools providing estimations of the same variable obtained with different spatial and time resolutions. Comparisons and the understanding of the uncertainties may also provide insight and help reduce observational and modelling uncertainty in the future. Furthermore, these approaches show the potential impact of a holistic approach on the final description of processes occurring in the Arctic ecosystem.

3. Summary

The description of the snow cover represents important knowledge useful for the calibration and validation of the snow process and hydrological models. From this perspective, the availability of long time series is a critical task that can be approached using ground-based as well as remotely sensed data. The current SESS report includes three different chapters about data sources that can provide important datasets with different time and spatial resolutions. These differences are not a limitation but represent an opportunity to develop a multi-scale analysis and obtain reliable input for climate and ecological models. The chapter 'PASSES' ([Salzano et al. 2021](#)), focuses on terrestrial photography applications, provides an overview of the cameras operating in Svalbard looking at specific applications on the snow cover and collecting information about the images discoverable and/or accessible on the web. These data sources can provide information about the state of the snow cover that is limited in terms of spatial extension (10 m² up to 10 km²) but almost independent from the meteorological conditions and characterised by high time resolution.

The availability of a network of cameras, potentially operating for a long time (the longest time series covers about 20 years), offers the opportunity to have continuous ground truth for validating remotely sensed data. Looking for an upscaling

strategy from in situ observations to satellite data, terrestrial photography can be easily linked to the satellite sensors characterised by higher spatial resolution (Sentinel-2, Landsat 8, etc.). This is the case with the results presented in the third chapter 'SATMODSNOW' ([Malnes et al. 2021](#)), where sensors characterised by higher spatial resolution are considered. Data provided by AVHRR, MODIS and Sentinel-2 Multi-Spectral Instrument (MSI) cover the 2000–2020 time interval, providing a snow cover description with a spatial resolution ranging from 4 km to 10 m and time resolution spanning from 5 days to half a day. In SATMODSNOW, several hydrological snow models were compared with snow cover fractions from satellites. The comparisons show that there are significant differences between the datasets, both with respect to the geographical snow distribution and the timing of the snow cover. The main reason for the differences is possibly inaccurate precipitation/temperature inputs to the snow models. Improvements are foreseen in the future when snow models can assimilate satellite data as well.

Furthermore, the description of the snow cover seasonality at different spatial scales contributes to the assessment of climate changes. Potentialities have been highlighted in this direction by the chapter 'SvalSCESIA' based on the AVHRR platform

(Killie et al. 2021). This dataset covers the 1982–2015 time interval and provides a snow cover description with a 4 km spatial resolution and a daily time resolution. Satellite monitoring showed an earlier onset of snow melting in Svalbard, with the most pronounced decrease in the valleys by 1–2 days/year. The variability of the snow cover in the lowlands correlates with the variability of sea ice in the adjacent sea, especially in the month of June. This chapter confirmed the need to develop a data model fusion system that would merge the available observational datasets on snow properties

with state-of-the-art, high-resolution (1 to 500 m scale) and physically based snow models. The goal of this data-enhancement system is the creation of accurate, spatially distributed and time-evolving datasets for better understanding the relationships between ecosystem processes. Additionally, integration with other snow parameters such as snow depth, snow water equivalent and snow-cover extent datasets (especially archival dating back to the 80s) would be extremely helpful in the calibration and validation of long-term satellite products and models.

Figure: The representation of a multi-scale strategy aimed at solving the gap existing between in situ measurements and satellite observations: the snow cover observed from different perspectives. The gaps between different spatial and temporal scales need to be bridged using sensors in the intermediate scale range (e.g., airborne sensors) to understand and remove uncertainties in long-term snow time series based on coarse-scaled satellite data and modelling.

4. Joint recommendations

- Intercomparisons (and intercalibrations) of snow products from coarse scale (4km, AVHRR), via medium scale (500m, MODIS) and detailed (10–20m, S2-MSI) to sub-meter scale (time-lapse cameras) could be investigated; this will help in better understanding detailed melting patterns.
- A SIOS/Svalbard supersite for remote sensing of snow should be established to provide sustained in situ reference snow measurements that can be used for cal/val activities.
- Attempts should be made to map, harvest and maintain (if possible) all kinds of EO products of snow over the archipelago and validate/quantify errors in each of the datasets.
- The assimilation of EO data in snow hydrology and snow process models needs to be further investigated.

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